

Reflective Report

(Organisational Behaviour)

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Abstract

This reflective report aims to summarise and provide insights on the topics covered in the organisational behaviour module. Four main topics reflected in this report are individual differences, motivation, interpersonal communication, and leadership in organisation. The report includes the importance of reflective report as well as a brief introduction for every topic covered. In addition, the author's understanding on the topics and how it relates to the real-life application are also included. lastly in the conclusion the author summarizes the importance of this module.

Keywords: Reflective report, organisational behaviour.

Introduction

A reflective report is an important task that is used in coursework and work placement that allows for a thoughtful reflection on activities and roles that make a link in relating experience to theory (Dwyer, 2013). This report serves as journal of learning and reflection on organisational behaviour module throughout lectures and discussion. According to O'Connell and Dymont (2006), reflective report can be an effective studying strategy. It helps students to reflect critically on material given, to show that they understand the knowledge they learned and how they adapt the knowledge to their personal life. As mention by Kerka (2002), reflective report helps students process their knowledge and articulate the connection between the new information that they get and existing knowledge that they have. This method enables the students to improve their learning techniques as they can reflect back on what they have learnt and deepen their understanding.

Reflection

Individual Differences, Mental Ability and Personality

The first topic covered in this module is about individual differences, mental ability, and personality. Individual differences refer to the distinguishing factors of individuals. For example, according to Baumeister and Vohs (2007), individual differences can be defined in terms of enduring psychological characteristics. Some of the important factors that is important in distinguishing individuals are mental ability, personality traits and values.

For this particular topic, students were asked to do research before attending the class on individual differences on a well-known company. There are about sixty students and each of them present their research on the company that they selected. In my case, I chose Shopify as my example for this topic. From this research I learnt that Shopify emphasize the importance of

individual differences in their company. They highlighted four key points to access individual differences in their recruitment process which are trust, engagement, self-awareness, and readiness.

From this topic, I also learnt that every individual has their own strengths and weaknesses. In order to success, we need to understand ourselves on how we are different from others and make use of the skills and knowledge that we have. Furthermore, by understanding our value, we will be able to determine the career path that suits our mental ability as well as personality.

Motivations

According to Robbins and Judge (2008), motivation can be defined as “The processes that account for an individual’s intensity, direction and persistence of effort towards attaining a goal.” There are many theories can be used to classify individual’s motivation. Some of the most important theories of motivation are Maslow’s Need Hierarchy Theory, McClelland’s Need Theory, and Vroom’s Expectancy Theory.

Before attending the class, my perception on motivation is very general. I see motivation as something that drives an individual to do something. After attending the class and reading the materials given, I see that motivation can further be characterized into intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. Intrinsic motivation refers to an act of doing something because it is personally rewarding. While extrinsic motivation involves doing something in order to earn a reward or avoid punishment.

Furthermore, students were given task to use theories and concept of motivation to understand the reason that motivate them to pursue their Masters. From this task, I organised the motivation factors that inspire me in pursuing my Masters of Logistics. This help me to better understand myself and it shows that I am driven mostly by Intrinsic motivation.

On the other hand, most of my motivations are derived from the Need Theory of motivation. It shows that I am driven by the McClelland’s Need Theory where the theory of needs focuses on achievement, power, and affiliation. It is true based on my personal opinion, I am most of the time motivated by personal desire where I drive to excel and strive to succeed.

Interpersonal communications

interpersonal communication allows individuals to exchange information to help them coordinate their actions to produce the relational rewards necessary for relational maintenance and growth (Fry, 2008). Interpersonal skills are important for communicating and working with groups and individuals for their personal and professional life. People with strong interpersonal skills are more likely to build good relationships and able to work well with others.

During the class, students were asked to make a group of two and discuss among themselves about an event where they feel mad when working in a group and how they handle the issue. For

my case, I explain on how I stumble into incorrect excel formulae when I was inputting data in my previous part time job. During the event, I tried to explain the problem to my colleagues, but they are unable to understand very well as they have limited knowledge in terms of mathematical formulation. Therefore, I raise the issue to the accountant department because the problem is related to the cost spent by the company. Fortunately, the accountant understands the problem and provide some feedback on how to solve it.

From this discussion, I learnt that there are a lot of different issues that may happen between individuals. If the issue is related to asymmetric information between individuals therefore an effective communication and channel the problem to the right person may help to solve the issue most of the time.

Leadership in Organisations

Organisation relies on effective leadership for its continuous development and growth (Ahn, Adamson, and Dornbusch, 2004). According to Schimmoeller (2010), the success of an organisation depends upon the adaptability of leaders in selecting appropriate leadership style. Moreover, in order for an organisation to achieve its goals and objectives, the need for effective leadership is required to ensure motivation and satisfaction of the employees (Bass and Avolio, 1994). There are various leadership theories can be used to access individual's leadership style for examples Lewin's leadership and integrated leadership system (ILS) theories.

For this module I did a case study on the perspective of culture and leadership in the public education sector in Brunei Darussalam. In my research I adapted Lewin's leadership theory to determine the leadership style practiced in the organisation. I found that the dominant leadership style practiced is the participative leadership style followed by directive and delegative leadership styles, respectively.

From this topic, I learnt that each type of leadership style has its own strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, in order to manage a group or organisation effectively, leaders need to change and adapt their leadership style accordingly.

Conclusion

From this reflective report, it shows that various topics were covered in order to understand organisational behaviour. The topics are contemporary and keeps on changing over time. Various theories used to understand the aspects of organisational behaviour. According to Musa and Idris (2020), students lack the awareness of the skills that were expected by employers. Therefore, this module helps to provide students the understanding of how organisation perceives their employees.

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